

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19151586

Effect Of Exchange Rate Reforms On Private Sector Investment In Nigeria

Dr Okpala O.V. & Dr Chime, Uzoamaka Francisca

¹Department of Banking and Finance
Tansian University, Umunya, Anambra State, Nigeria
Ositadimma1995@gmail.com

²Department of Business Administration,
Tansian University, Umunya, Anambra State, Nigeria
chukwusom2017@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria for the period of 1987 to 2021. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of exchange rate and foreign reserved on private sector investment. The variables were private sector investment as the dependent variables while exchange rate and foreign reserved were the independent variables. These variables were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria bulletin. Secondary type of data were utilized in this study, the population of the study was deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited, The Autoregressive Distributive Lag approach was employed for the analysis The study found that total banking sector credit to private sector has positive significant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria, money supply has positive significant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. The study concludes that while exchange rate reforms are important for macroeconomic management, their impact on private sector investment in Nigeria has been weak and ineffective. The study recommends that Policymakers should prioritize exchange rate stability over frequent policy changes. A predictable and stable exchange rate environment will reduce uncertainty, improve investor confidence, and encourage long-term private sector investment. Exchange rate reforms should be implemented alongside supportive monetary and fiscal policies aimed at controlling inflation, reducing interest rates, and improving access to credit for private sector investors.

Keywords: exchange rate reforms, foreign reserved, private sector investment, Autoregressive Distributive Lag approach

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Exchange rate policy is a critical macroeconomic instrument through which governments influence external competitiveness, capital flows, and overall economic performance. In developing economies such as Nigeria, exchange rate reforms have remained a central component of economic adjustment programmes aimed at correcting balance of payments disequilibria, stabilizing the macroeconomic environment, and stimulating productive investment (Adamson, Onyeka-Iheme & Akinrinola, 2025). The private sector, being the engine of economic growth, is particularly sensitive to exchange rate movements and policy reforms, as these directly affect the cost of imported inputs, export earnings, profitability, and

investment decisions. Frequent fluctuations in the value of the naira, coupled with policy inconsistencies and foreign exchange scarcity, have increased uncertainty for private investors. This uncertainty affects planning horizons, raises the cost of capital, and may discourage both domestic and foreign private investment (Ajayi, Adebayo, & Osunkunle 2025).

Exchange rate reforms can influence private sector investment through several channels. A depreciation of the exchange rate may stimulate investment in export-oriented industries by improving competitiveness, while simultaneously increasing production costs for firms heavily dependent on imported machinery and raw materials (Egbaseimokumo, 2024). Similarly, a stable and predictable exchange rate regime can enhance investor confidence, reduce risk premiums, and promote long-term investment planning. Conversely, persistent exchange rate instability may undermine private sector performance by increasing operational risks and reducing expected returns on investment (Farouq, Musa, & Muhammad, 2025).

Despite the numerous exchange rate reforms implemented in Nigeria, private sector investment performance has remained inconsistent over the years. While some periods have recorded modest improvements in investment levels, others have been characterized by declining private sector activity, factory closures, and capital flight. This raises critical questions about the effectiveness of exchange rate reforms in stimulating private sector investment and whether the intended policy objectives have been achieved (Nwinkina Wadi, Kenigheni & Edi, 2025).

It is against this backdrop that this study examines the effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. The study seeks to provide empirical evidence on how changes in exchange rate policy and movements in the exchange rate influence private sector investment decisions, with a view to informing policy formulation and promoting a more investment-friendly macroeconomic environment.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Exchange rate reforms have been a recurring policy response by the Nigerian government to address macroeconomic imbalances, improve foreign exchange management, and stimulate economic growth. Over the years, several reforms ranging from exchange rate liberalization, devaluation, foreign exchange market unification, and the introduction of various foreign exchange windows have been implemented with the expectation that a more efficient and market-driven exchange rate system would enhance private sector investment and overall economic performance. Despite these reforms, private sector investment in Nigeria has remained volatile and, in some periods, significantly below its potential. One major concern is the persistent instability and unpredictability of the exchange rate in Nigeria. Frequent fluctuations in the value of the naira have created an uncertain business environment, making it difficult for private investors to accurately forecast costs, revenues, and returns on investment. This uncertainty is particularly damaging for long-term investment decisions, as it increases investment risk and discourages both domestic and foreign private sector participation in productive economic activities.

Furthermore, the coexistence of multiple exchange rate regimes and policy inconsistencies over time has weakened investor confidence. Frequent policy reversals and administrative interventions in the foreign exchange market have distorted price signals and limited the effectiveness of exchange rate reforms. As a result, private investors face difficulties in accessing foreign exchange at predictable rates, thereby undermining their ability to plan and execute investment projects efficiently. Empirical evidence on the relationship between exchange rate reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria also remains inconclusive. While some studies suggest that exchange rate liberalization promotes investment through improved competitiveness and capital inflows, others argue that exchange rate volatility and depreciation have adverse effects on private sector investment. The mixed findings in existing literature highlight the need for a country-specific and updated empirical investigation that captures Nigeria's unique economic structure and recent exchange rate policy developments. In light of these challenges, the effectiveness of exchange rate reforms in stimulating private sector investment in Nigeria remains questionable. There is therefore a need for a comprehensive empirical study to examine the extent to which exchange rate reforms have influenced private sector investment in Nigeria,

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the effect of exchange rate on private sector investment in Nigeria;
- ii. Determine the effect of foreign reserved on private sector investment in Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Exchange Rate Reforms

Transactions in the foreign exchange constitute an important aspect of financial sector activities and arguably it is the largest and most extensive financial market in the world (Anyafu, 1996). This is because apart from being the vehicle for settlement of international transactions, it functions as the medium of interaction between sellers and buyers of foreign exchange in a bid to negotiate a mutually acceptable price for the promotion and furtherance of international transactions. The financial sector is hugely affected by activities in the foreign exchange market primarily because of the central role of banks in financial intermediation. Exchange rate is the price of one country's currency in relation to another country. It is the required amount of units of a currency that can buy another amount of units of another currency. Aliyu (2011) asserted that appreciation of exchange rate results in increased imports and reduced export while depreciation would expand export and discourage import. Also, depreciation of exchange rate tends to cause a shift from foreign goods to domestic goods. Hence, it leads to diversion of income from importing countries to countries exporting through a shift in terms of trade, and this tends to have impact on the exporting and importing countries' economic growth. In the same vein, Hossain (2002) agreed that exchange rate helps to connect the price systems of two different countries by making it possible for international trade and also effects on the volume of imports and exports, as well as country's balance of payments position. Rogoffs and Reinhartl (2004) also opined that developing countries are relatively better off in the choice of flexible exchange rate regimes. Adebisi and Dauda (2009) using error correction model argued on the contrary that trade liberalization promoted growth in the Nigerian industrial sector and stabilized the exchange rate market between 1970 and 2006. To them, there was a positive and significant relationship between index of industrial production and real export. A one percent rise in real export increase the index of industrial production by 12.2 percent. By implication, it means that the policy of deregulation impacted positively on export through exchange rate depreciation.

2.1.2 Private Sector Investment

The economy of every country has two broad participants which are the private sector and the public sector. The private sector is the part of a country's economic system that is run by individuals and companies, rather than a government entity. Investment by most private sector organizations are done with the intention of making profit.

In Keynesian terminology, investment refers to addition to capital equipment which enables an increase in the production of capital goods (Jhingan, 2002). The term, investment, according to Ibenta (2005), may be defined as accumulation and commitment of fund in financial and real assets with the objective of obtaining income over time. He further noted that it is a commitment of resources made in the hope of realising benefits that are expected to occur over a reasonably long period of time in the future. Investment can also be referred to as the production of capital goods (Heim, 2008). Investment thus includes new plant and equipment, construction of public works like roads, dams, buildings, etc. Investment can be defined as the outlay of money for future use (Agu, 2015).

Investment can be made by the corporate organisation for individual stakeholders or directly by the individual in a certain project. This is known as Private Investment. But, when the commitment of funds for productive purposes is done by the government for the betterment of the citizenry, it is called Public Investment.

Private sector investment in Nigeria is faced with some daunting challenges. For decades, Nigeria's economy was characterized by growing dominance of the public sector over the private sector. The

private sector faced numerous problems which include; the poor state of physical infrastructure, particularly road networks, electricity and water supply; inadequate credit to the private sector, which has dove-tailed to high cost of production; insecurity in the country; corruption at various levels; weak institutions, etc. (Okorie & Chikwendu, 2019).

The private sector plays a vital role in the economy by creating jobs, providing goods and services, and stimulating economic growth. The private sector is a key driver of innovation. As a result of this, private companies invest in research and development, which leads to new products and services that boost the economy, improve lives and tremendously enhance competitions with great revenues generated.

In free economies, the private sector makes up a big portion of the economy, as opposed to nations that have more state control over their economies, which have a larger public sector (Brock, 2020). The Government credits' support to the private sector is to enhance and engender economic viability. Credit to private sector refers to financial resources provided to the private sector, such as loans and advances, purchases of non-equity securities, trade credits and other accounts' receivable, which establish a claim for repayment. In this regard, credit can be viewed from two angles; namely: trade or commercial credit and banking system credit. Freear (1980), says trade credit refers to transactions which involve the supplier handing over goods or performing a service without receiving immediate payment but payment to be made in the future (Gbenga, James & Adeyinka, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) Theory.

The Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) simply states that a unit of any given currency should be able to buy the same quantity of goods in all countries. Many economists believe that the PPP describes the forces that determine exchange rates in the long run. Accordingly, the nominal exchange rate between the currencies of two countries must reflect the different prices level in those countries. PPP, which forms a strong building block of the theory of exchange rate determination, maintains that there exists a proportional relationship between the exchange rate of the currencies of two countries and their relative inflation rates. The theory is based on the law of one price, which explains that, in the absence of trade barriers and transportation costs, spatial commodity arbitrage ensures that the price of any good is equalized across different countries. The PPP theory can be formulated in two forms: in absolute forms. The absolute form of PPP asserts that the equilibrium exchange rate equalizes the general purchasing power of a given income in terms of relative price levels. It thus, relates the level of exchange rate to relative prices levels. The relative form argues that changes in exchange rate measured from a base period reflect changes in relative price levels.

2.3 Theoretical Exposition

Exchange Rate Reform and Private Investment Hypothesis

Exchange rate has been defined as a price at which one's country currency exchanges for that of another. Exchange rate movement and reforms have implications on macroeconomic variables include private sector investment. Studies have shown that exchange rate devaluation has an adverse effect on investment. For instance, the work of Chhibber and Shafik (1990) on Indonesia using a macroeconomic model with data from 1974 to 1987 confirmed that for the period between 1982 and 1987, it revealed that in the short-run, devaluation adversely affected private investment. It raised the import cost of equipment and machinery that led to the reduced returns on investment. However, investment was predicted to have recovered after about two to three years due to export expansion and an enhanced efficiency in production brought about by devaluation. Exchange rate depreciation often results in price inflation, and a recent result from nine developing countries (mostly Latin American Countries) support the theoretical expectation that inflation hinders private investment (Oyedele, 2013).

Recent literature has analytically focused on the adjustment costs caused by the acquisition and installation of capital which emphasized the irreversible nature of most fixed investment projects (Dixit & Pindyck 1994). This makes investment adjustment costs asymmetrically larger for downward than upward adjustment. Under appropriate conditions, this creates a range of inaction: investment takes place only when the difference between expected profitability and the cost of capital exceeds a certain

threshold. The reason is that firms become more reluctant to invest due to the risk of getting stuck with too much of their capital if events turn unfavourable. Even disturbances that raise the profitability of all investment projects, but make their relative ranking more uncertain, can lead to inaction and hence depress aggregate investment as investors try to avoid the irreversible mistake of investing in the wrong activity (Bernanke, 1983).

2.4 Empirical Study

Zardashty (2014) analyses the impacts of real exchange rate on private sector investment in Iran from 1961-2008 using an EGARCH model. The results indicate that the index of real exchange rate has a negative effect on private investment, GDP ratio, and imports of capital commodity. The result equally indicates that inflation has negative effects on private investment to GDP ratio.

Oyedele (2013) investigated the impact of exchange rate on the level of private investment in Nigeria from 1980 to 2010. The dependent variable is the ratio of private investment to GDP, whereas exchange rate variables were captured as real effective exchange rate, real per capita GDP, inflation rate and public investment growth rate. Data were obtained from World Development Indicators 2012. Results from co-integration and ECM revealed a negative relationship between the exchange rate and private investment.

Ani, Ugwunta and Okanya (2013) examined effect of foreign exchange reforms on the financial depth of the Nigerian economy for 29-year period spanning from 1982 to 2010. The explanatory variables were developed and selected in line with the theoretical framework. The OLS regressions were applied to the data to determine the overall effect of foreign exchange reforms on the financial depth of the economy. Findings revealed that ratio of FDI to GDP, ratio of market capitalization of listed equities to GDP and real interest rate have positive relationship with financial deepening while exchange rate has a negative relationship with financial deepening.

Okoye, Okoyrie, Okoh, Olokoyo and Ezeji (2019) examined the nexus between exchange rate policy and economic performance in Nigeria to determine growth-supportive policy option for a developing economy. Exchange rate effect on growth was analyzed under two distinct phases of exchange rate management: fixed (1970-1986) and floating (1987- 2016) regimes. The full impact assessment of exchange rate on economic growth was also examined for the entire period (1970-2016). Using the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model, the mean equation shows significant positive effect of exchange rate on growth over the full sample period and under the floating regime. Exchange rate effect on growth during the fixed regime was negative and non-significant. In terms of volatility, the study did not show significant evidence of exchange rate volatility over the full sample period and under the fixed regime. However, under the floating regime, there is evidence of strong negative volatility effect of exchange rate on economic growth. The study posits that exchange rate policy is a major determinant of economic performance in Nigeria.

Obi, Oniore and Nnadi (2016) examined the relationship between exchange rate regimes and output growth in Nigeria in different periods from 1970 to 2014. The study employs the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to estimate economic growth equation as a result of endogeneity problem. In contrast with previous findings, their study strongly suggests that exchange rate regimes indeed matter in terms of real economic performance in Nigeria as the results reveal that deregulated exchange rate regimes spur economic growth in Nigeria as against the whole period and fixed exchange rate regime. The study posits that fixed exchange rates constrain the performance of the Nigerian economy.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in this study. This design is suitable for secondary data studies, especially when the data has already been documented and authenticated by some great research based institutions like the World Bank, IMF, CBN among others (Kerlinger, 1973). It is a well-known fact that in this regression study, the researcher investigated a cause and effect relationship without manipulating the existing data.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data which are collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria publications. The data covered a period of thirty five (35) years (1987 to 2021). This period covered the post Structural Adjustment Programme era.

3.3 Model Specification

The model to address objective of the study is developed in this section. The model is premised on the assumption that exchange rate creates trade openness in the face of inflation to influence private sector investment. The functional model is as shown below:

$$PI = f(EXR, FS) \text{ -----Model 1}$$

Where:

PI = private sector investment

F= Functional notation

EXR = Exchange rate of Naira to Dollar.

FS = Foreign reserve

This can be rewritten in equation form as follows:

$$PI = c_0 + c_1EXR + c_2FS + \mu \text{ -----Eqn 2}$$

c_0 is the autonomous value of the constant while c_{1-2} are the coefficients of the independent variables. The μ is the error term that smoothens the stochastic effect of time series disturbances on the model.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

This study adopts econometric techniques in testing the effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment. It employs time series data necessitates stationarity tests in order to avoid spurious results. The unit root test is expected to determine the nature of the time series data and the most suitable tool of regression technique to employ. It is expected that in cases where all the variables are stationary at level 1(0), the Ordinary Least Square tends to be the most suitable regression technique, whereas the Johansson cointegration works better in situation where all the variables take the forms of first order integration 1(1). In cases where the econometric variables have a combination of both level 1(0) and first integration 1(1), the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) works best.

3.5 A priori Expectation

The a priori expectation in each of the models is as follows: $\beta > 0$; this explains the theoretical linkage on the sign and magnitude of parameter of the specified functions. The Sign (>) indicates an improvement on Private Sector Investment as the dependent variable. This supposes that increase in any variable in the exchange rate reforms paradigm increases by a unit.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests was employed to determine the stationarity or otherwise of variables used in the study. The ADF tests are done on level series, and first order difference series. The decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, otherwise, accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value.

Table 1: Summary of Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Variables	At Level	1(0)	At First Difference		Order of Integration
	T-stat	P.Value	T-stat	P.value	
Private Sector Investment (PI)	-3.929579	0.0056	-	-	1(0)
Foreign reserve (FS)	-4.452938	0.0012	-	-	1(0)
Exchange rate (EXR)	1.771571	0.9995	-5.793617	0.0000	1(1)

The stationarity test otherwise called unit root analysis shows that some of the variables are stationary at level {that is had no unit root at 1(0)}such as Private Sector Investment and Foreign reserve while

Exchange rate were not stationary at level but become stationary in their first differences {that is, they had no unit roots at 1(1)}.

4.2 Estimation of Long run Effect of exchange rate Reforms on Private Sector Investment

The test of cointegration for the presence of a long-run relationship in the models is shown in Table 2. The ARDL result was used to compare the bound critical values with the F-statistics values. The decision rule: If the F-statistic is above the upper and lower critical bound values, then there is a long run relationship in the model; but where the F-statistics is below the upper and lower bound critical values, it is inferred that there is no long-run effect (relationship). The null hypothesis is that “No long-run relationship exists”.

Table 2: ARDL Bounds Test for long run effect of exchange rate on private sector investment

Models	F-Statistic	Lower Critical Value Bound at 5% level	Upper Critical Value Bound at 5% level
Exchange Rate Reforms	49.8465*	2.45	3.61

*significant at 5%

From the results in Table2, the critical bound values were computed at 5% level of significance. The lower critical bound value is 2.45 while the upper critical value is 3.61. The F-statistics for the model is 49.8465, respectively. The F-statistics for all the models are greater than the Upper (3.61) and Lower (2.45) critical bound values. Thus we rejected the null hypotheses for the models and conclude presence of long run relationship in all the models.

4.3 Analyses of Long Run Effects of Exchange Rate Reforms on Private Sector Investment

Table 2: Model of the long run relationship between exchange rate reform and private sector investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PI(-1))	1.963033	0.265320	7.398739	0.0001
D(PI(-2))	-2.554944	0.399914	-6.388734	0.0002
D(EXR)	-0.000686	0.000155	-4.430396	0.0022
D(EXR(-1))	0.000269	0.000224	1.198012	0.2652
D(EXR(-2))	-0.001508	0.000309	-4.877527	0.0012
D(FS)	-0.000619	0.000580	-1.067880	0.3167
D(FS(-1))	0.000907	0.000916	0.990829	0.3508
CointEq(-1)	-0.126818	0.164043	-0.773081	0.4617
Cointeq = PI - (0.0057*EXR -0.0003*FS -0.4000)				
Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	0.005658	0.005365	1.054512	0.3225
FS	-0.000327	0.010515	-0.031087	0.9760
C	-0.400042	0.767976	-0.520905	0.6165

The result on Table 2 analyzes the nature and significance of the relationship between exchange rate reform and private sector investment. The analysis of the long run equilibrium was captured by the error correction of -0.1268 and a probability value of 0.4617. The coefficient showed a negative sign suggesting the possibility of a return on long run equilibrium. However, since the p.value is greater than 0.05, which means presence of insignificant speed of adjustment. This indicates that a deviation from the long run trend will not be effectively adjusted to normal trend over time. Thus the study posits that exchange rate reform does not have a significant long-run policy effect on the private sector investment in Nigeria.

The results on Table 10 implies that exchange rate reform has not played instrumental roles in driving private sector investment in Nigeria. The long-run coefficients of regression confirmed the insignificant long-run effects since all the exchange rate variables (EXR, FS) have p.values that are greater than 0.05.

4.4 Short run Effect of Exchange Rate Reform on Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Exchange Rate Reform and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PI(-1)	2.836215	0.167850	16.89736	0.0000
PI(-2)	-4.517977	0.428311	-10.54836	0.0000
PI(-3)	2.554944	0.399914	6.388734	0.0002
EXR	-0.000686	0.000155	-4.430396	0.0022
EXR(-1)	0.000165	0.000143	1.150129	0.2833
EXR(-2)	-0.000269	0.000224	-1.198012	0.2652
EXR(-3)	0.001508	0.000309	4.877527	0.0012
FS	-0.000619	0.000580	-1.067880	0.3167
FS(-1)	0.001485	0.000663	2.240944	0.0553
FS(-2)	-0.000907	0.000916	-0.990829	0.3508
C	-0.050733	0.079321	-0.639590	0.5403
R-squared	0.999929			
Adjusted R-squared	0.999733			
F-statistic	5116.111			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Durbin-Watson stat	3.105610			

The result showed that private sector investment (PI) endogenously influences exchange rate reform within the first (-1), second (-2) and third (-3) year of funding. It had a positive effect after the first year and the third year but negative effect after the second year. This means that a unit change in PI will drive subsequent year investment either to the increase in the first and third year or decrease in the second year. This portends that private sector investment for a given year determines the level of inputs and hence expectations of output in the up-coming short run periods.

Funding from exchange rate (EXR) has a negative (-0.0006) and significant (0.0022) short-run effects after the first year, but a positive (0.0015) and significant (0.0012) short-run effect after the third year. However, foreign reserve had not statistically significant coefficients within the short run periods.

On the overall, the adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R₂) revealed that about 99% of the change in private sector investment (PI) can be explained by exchange rate reform in Nigeria. This is confirmed by a significantly significant p.value of 0.0000 from the F-statistics (5116.11). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 3.11 suggests a suspicion on the confounding influence of trends on the reliability of the model.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment

Exchange rate reforms have a 99% significant short run policy effect but no significant long run effects on private sector investment in Nigeria. The implication is that exchange rate reforms in Nigeria does not have long run effect on private sector investment. The short run exchange rate reforms in Nigeria is enabled by third lag positive influence from exchange rate regime (0.0015, $p = 0.0012$). Hence, foreign reserve has not contributed to the private sector investment in Nigeria.

The previous studies were of the view that exchange rate reforms have negative effect on private investment and growth of the economy (Okoye *et al*, 2019; Oyedele, 2013 and Ani, *et al*, 2013) from Nigeria and (Zardashty, 2014; Ahmad *et al*, 2013) from Iran and Paksitan respectively. Their findings were also in alignment with foreign exchange theory where in excessive depreciation badly affects other economic indicators that include private investment. This is not in tandem with the positive relationship that this present study reveals and supports (Hussain *et al*, 2019; Mwinlaar & Ofori, 2017) from Pakistan and Ghana respectively.

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the effect of exchange rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria with a view to determining whether changes in exchange rate policy have significantly influenced private sector investment decisions. The empirical findings revealed that the exchange rate variable exerted a negative and statistically insignificant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria during the period under review. The negative coefficient suggests that exchange rate reforms, particularly those associated with currency depreciation and volatility, tend to discourage private sector investment by increasing uncertainty and the cost of imported capital inputs. However, the insignificance of the relationship indicates that exchange rate movements alone have not been a dominant factor influencing private sector investment in Nigeria.. The findings further imply that the numerous exchange rate reforms implemented in Nigeria have not translated into meaningful improvements in private sector investment. This may be attributed to persistent exchange rate instability, frequent policy changes, and structural weaknesses in the economy that limit the private sector's ability to respond positively to exchange rate adjustments. The study concludes that while exchange rate reforms are important for macroeconomic management, their impact on private sector investment in Nigeria has been weak and ineffective. A more holistic policy approach is therefore required to create a stable and enabling environment that can support sustained private sector investment and economic growth. The study recommends that Policymakers should prioritize exchange rate stability over frequent policy changes. A predictable and stable exchange rate environment will reduce uncertainty, improve investor confidence, and encourage long-term private sector investment. Exchange rate reforms should be implemented alongside supportive monetary and fiscal policies aimed at controlling inflation, reducing interest rates, and improving access to credit for private sector investors. Government should promote local production of capital goods and intermediate inputs through industrial policies, incentives for domestic manufacturing, and support for value-chain development.

REFERENCES

- Adamson, M.A, Onyeka-Iheme C.V, & Akinrinola, O (2025). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research* 13(3)405-416,
- Adebiyi, M. A and Dauda, R.O.S. (2009). Trade liberalization policy and industrialization growth performance in Nigeria: An error correction mechanism technique being a paper presented at the 45th annual conference of Nigeria economic society 24th to 26th August, central Bank of Nigeria new building auditorium, Abuja.
- Agu, O. C. (2015). Determinants of private investment in Nigeria: An econometric analysis. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, III (4), 1 – 14.

- Ajayi L. B. , Adebayo A. O. , & Osunkunle U. A. (2025). Exchange Rate Fluctuations and Selected Deposit Money Banks Performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 11 (10) 56-78
- Ani, W.U., Ugwunta, D. O., & Okanya, O. (2013). The Effect of foreign exchange reforms on financial deepening: Evidence from Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and*
- Bernanke, B. S. (1983). Nonmonetary Effects of the Financial Crisis in Propagation of the Great Depression. *American Economic Review*, 73(3), 257-276.
- Brock, T. (2020). Private sector definition. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/private-sector.asp>
- Dixit, A. K., & Pindyck, R. S. (1994). *Investment under Uncertainty*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400830176>
- Egbaseimokumo, O.P (2024). The Effect of Exchange Rate on the Growth of the Nigerian Economy. *international journal of research and innovation in social science*, 8 (7) 1872-1899
- Farouq, K. M., Musa, H. M. & Muhammad, R. S. (2025). the impact of exchange rate and economy growth of nigeria (1980 - 2023). *Journal of Accounting and Business Management*, 2 (11),5-12.
- Gbenga, O., James, S. O. & Adeyinka, A. J. (2019). Determinant of Private Sector Credit and Its Implication on Economic Growth in Nigeria: 2000-2017. Retrieved from <https://www.cribfb.com/journal/index.php/aesr/article/view/242/299>
- Heim, J. J. (2008). The Investment function: determinants of demand for investment. *Working Papers in Economics*.
- Hossain, A. (2002), Exchange rate response to inflation in Bangladesh
- Hussain, I.A.S., Hussain, J., Khan, A. A., Khan. Y. (2019). An analysis of the asymmetric impact of Exchange Rate change on GDP in Pakistan: Application of non-Linear ARDL. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja*, 32:1, 3100-3117.
- Ibenta, S. O. N. (2005). *Investment analysis and financial management strategy*. Enugu: Institute for Development Studies.
- Jhingan, M.L. (2011). *Money banking, international trade and public finance*, 8th Edition.
- Nwikina C. G., Wadi, E.O, Kenigheni G. W., & Edi, M.F (2025). Exchange Rate and Performance of Manufacturing Industry in Nigeria; *Glob Acad J Econ Buss*, 7(1), 28-39.
- Obi, K.O., Oniore, J. O. & Nnadi, K. U. (2016). The impact of exchange rate regimes on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 7(12), 115-127
- Okorie, G. C. & Chikwendu, N. F. (2019). Does private sector credit impact on private sector investment in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, VI(XII), 23 – 28.
- Okoye, L.U., Okorie, U. E., Okoh, I., Olokoyo, F. O. & Ezeji, F. N. (2019). Exchange rate dynamics and economic performance: Evidence from Nigeria, *Proceedings of SOCIONT 2019*, 6th International Conference on Education, Social Sciences and Humanities 24-26 June, Istanbul, Turkey
- Oyedele, O. (2013). The exchange rate and private investment in Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 40(4), 638 – 648.
- Zardashty, G. R. (2014). ‘The impact of real exchange rate uncertainty on private investment in Iran’, *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(10), 1-2.